

THE CHALLENGES MOST STUDENTS ENCOUNTER DURING LISTENING SKILL

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Abstract. The listening skill can be challenging for students due to various factors. Some of the common challenges include understanding accents and pronunciation, dealing with unfamiliar vocabulary, coping with background noise and distractions, following complex instructions, struggling with note-taking skills, lack of practice, anxiety and lack of confidence, and difficulty understanding different accents and dialects. Understanding accents and pronunciation can be difficult for students as they may not be accustomed to hearing speakers with different accents or those who speak quickly. This can make it hard to catch all the words and comprehend the overall message.

Keywords: challenges, students, developing, listening skills, understanding accents, fast-paced speech, unfamiliar vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, background noise, lacking visual cues, complex sentence structures, concentration, effective notes, multiple speakers, anxiety, self-confidence, educators, support, strategies, improve listening abilities.

Listening exercises often involve new vocabulary or unfamiliar words, which can be challenging for students to understand the meaning of what they are hearing. This can hinder their overall comprehension. Background noise and distractions can make it harder for students to focus on what they are listening to. In real-life situations, there may be various noises or distractions that affect their ability to accurately comprehend the information. Following complex instructions can also pose a challenge for students. Listening tasks may involve multiple instructions or complex information that students find difficult to process and remember. Taking notes while listening can be a struggle for some students. They may find it challenging to identify the main points or key information and end up missing important details. Lack of practice is another challenge students may face [3]. Listening is a skill that requires regular practice to improve. If students do not have enough exposure to listening activities or opportunities to practice, they may struggle to develop their listening skills effectively. Anxiety and lack of confidence can also impact students' listening abilities. Some students may feel anxious or lack confidence when it comes to listening tasks, which can affect their ability to concentrate and understand the information being presented. Lastly, understanding different accents and dialects can be challenging for students. English is spoken in various accents and dialects around the world, and students may find it difficult to understand speakers with different accents, especially if they have limited exposure to them. To overcome these challenges, students can practice listening regularly. They can expose themselves to a variety of accents and speakers, work on improving their vocabulary, develop note-taking skills, and seek opportunities to engage in real-life listening situations. Additionally, using resources such as podcasts, videos, and online exercises can also help students improve their listening skills [5, 257-270].

There are various activities that can help students overcome these challenges and improve their listening skills. Here are some activities that can be used to address the common difficulties faced by most students during the listening skill:

1. Dictation exercises: Dictation exercises can help students improve their listening accuracy and reinforce spelling and vocabulary. By providing short audio clips and having students write down what they hear, they can practice listening for specific words and phrases.
2. Gap-fill exercises: Gap-fill exercises provide students with a transcript of a listening passage with certain words or phrases missing. By playing the audio and having students fill in the gaps with the correct words they hear, they can focus on specific vocabulary and sentence structures.
3. Multiple-choice questions: Multiple-choice questions based on a listening passage can help students practice listening for specific information and making inferences. By listening to the audio and choosing the correct answer from the options provided, students can improve their listening comprehension skills.
4. Role-playing activities: Role-playing activities involve dividing students into pairs or small groups and giving them a scenario to act out based on a listening passage. This activity helps improve listening comprehension and speaking skills as students must listen carefully to their partner's dialogue in order to respond appropriately [1, 81-101].
5. Discussion-based activities: After listening to a passage, engaging students in a group discussion or debate about the topic can encourage critical thinking, expression of opinions, and practice of speaking skills.
6. Song lyrics analysis: Analyzing song lyrics can expose students to different types of English language expressions and improve their listening comprehension skills. By playing a song and having students listen for specific words or phrases mentioned in the lyrics, they can practice their listening skills in a fun and engaging way.
7. Storytelling activities: Playing an audio recording of a short story or narrative and having students retell the story in their own words can help them practice listening for main ideas, sequencing events, and storytelling skills.
8. Listening journals: Assigning students to keep a listening journal where they write about their experiences with listening to English outside of the classroom can encourage regular practice and reflection on listening skills.
9. Peer feedback: Pairing students up and having them listen to each other's recorded presentations or speeches can help them develop their listening skills while also giving them an opportunity to practice giving feedback.
10. Authentic listening tasks: Providing students with real-world listening tasks, such as listening to a radio interview or watching a TED talk, and having them complete a task based on the listening material, such as writing a summary or answering comprehension questions, can expose them to authentic language use and help them develop their listening skills in real-life contexts.
11. Podcasts. Students can listen to podcasts to improve their comprehension. They can also create podcasts to practice their English speaking abilities. A free download of iTunes gives teachers access to hundreds of free podcasts on a range of topics. There are multiple podcasts tailored specifically for English language learners. Teachers can also have students create podcasts to give them opportunities to practice their speaking skills. With just a microphone and a computer, students can create reports and presentations. Video podcasts are an

attractive option for students, and some classes even have their own YouTube channel [6, 180-182].

By incorporating these activities into language learning classrooms, teachers can help students overcome the challenges they face during the listening skill and improve their overall listening proficiency.

Conclusion. In conclusion, students face a variety of challenges when it comes to developing their listening skills. These challenges include understanding different accents, keeping up with fast-paced speech, encountering unfamiliar vocabulary and idiomatic expressions, dealing with background noise, lacking visual cues, struggling with complex sentence structures, maintaining concentration, taking effective notes, following conversations with multiple speakers, and dealing with anxiety and self-confidence issues. It is important for educators to be aware of these challenges and provide appropriate support and strategies to help students overcome them and improve their listening abilities.

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